

**EFFECT OF RESIN TOUGHNESS ON DELAMINATION
GROWTH IN COMPOSITE LAMINATES**

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ABSTRACT

Unidirectional and quasi-isotropic GFRP laminates have been prepared using a standard epoxy resin and with additions of urethane up to 20 % by weight of the epoxy. Fracture toughness tests showed that the addition of 20 % urethane increased both the Mode I and Mode II interlaminar fracture toughnesses, by 70 % and 40 % respectively, compared to the base epoxy. The initiation and growth of matrix cracking and edge delamination in the quasi-isotropic GFRP laminates under quasi-static loading have been studied. The onset of matrix cracking and delamination are both delayed in the urethane-containing material. The applicability of the compliance expression for the strain energy release rate to modelling the delamination initiation and growth is discussed.

KEY WORDS: Delamination, matrix cracking, fracture, toughness, stiffness loss

1. INTRODUCTION

Delamination (i.e. matrix crack growth between adjacent plies) can occur in composite laminates under static and fatigue loading conditions. In components (as opposed to laboratory test coupons) the sites at which delamination initiation and growth is likely to be of most concern are at holes or cut-outs, geometric discontinuities (including ply drop-offs) or at some sub-surface interface after impact damage.

It is well documented in the literature [1,2] that the onset of edge delamination in laminates can be predicted using strain energy release rate based analyses. It is also well established that the strain at which delamination initiates may be delayed by the use of tough matrices, although there is not yet agreement as to a generalised mixed mode failure criterion, e.g. [3-6]. However the subsequent growth of the delamination in laminates is complicated because of the development of matrix cracking in off-axis plies behind the advancing delamination crack front as studied by Poursartip [7], who modelled the phenomenon by noting that the effective delamination toughness

increases as a result of the extra energy associated with the matrix cracking.

The present study is concerned with how edge delamination initiation and growth in laminates depend on the resin matrix properties, which in turn affect the composite interlaminar fracture toughnesses G_{IC} and G_{IIC} . The test material is a model transparent GFRP system for which the matrix properties can be modified by the addition of polyurethane [8]. The Mode I and Mode II interlaminar fracture toughnesses of the lamina are measured using fracture mechanics tests and then the initiation and growth of delamination and its interaction with matrix cracking are studied using a quasi-isotropic lay-up which delaminates under quasi-static loading.

2. MATERIALS

The glass fibre/epoxy system used in the present work is manufactured from pre-preg produced in-house using a drum winding facility described elsewhere [8]. The resin properties are varied by adding a single component polyurethane (up to 20 % by weight of the epoxy) prior to processing. The resin is a proprietary formulation based on diglycidial ester of bisphenol-A (DGEBA) cured with a boron trifluoride complex. The matrices are reinforced with an E-glass fibre of modulus 70 GPa at a volume fraction of about 68 % in the cured laminates. Unidirectional laminates 4.3 mm thick (24 plies) with mid-plane PTFE inserts were prepared for fracture mechanics testing with urethane levels of 0, 5, 10 and 20 %. Quasi-isotropic laminates of lay-up $(+45/-45/0/90)_s$, 1.5 mm thick (8 ply), were produced with urethane levels of 0 and 20 % for making edge delamination specimens. The cured laminates were transparent and of good quality, making damage observation straightforward. Unidirectional properties for the unmodified epoxy laminate and the laminate containing 20 % urethane are shown in Table 1. Note that the urethane does not affect a fibre dominated property such as the longitudinal modulus E_1 but reduces significantly the matrix dominated elastic constants, the transverse modulus E_2 and the in-plane shear modulus G_{12} .

Table 1 Unidirectional ply properties for unmodified epoxy and 20 % urethane GFRP systems

Percentage urethane	E_1 , GPa	E_2 , GPa	ν_{12}	G_{12} , GPa
0 (unmodified epoxy)	47.8	17.2	0.25	5.8
20	47.8	14.8	0.26	4.3

3. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

3.1 Fracture Mechanics Tests Double cantilever beams (DCB) and end-notched-flexure (ENF) specimens [9,10] were cut from the unidirectional laminates to the dimensions shown in Figure 1. All specimens were loaded under displacement control at a cross-head displacement rate of 0.5 mm/min. For the ENF specimens the load at which crack propagation began was recorded, while for the DCB specimens the load-displacement curve was obtained enabling the R-curve behaviour to be inferred.

3.2 Tests on Quasi-isotropic Laminates Tensile test coupons 220 mm by 25 mm were cut from the $(+45/-45/0/90)_s$ laminates. Prior to testing, aluminium tags were bonded on to the ends of the specimen for ease of gripping in Instron wedge grips. Testing was carried out using an Instron under displacement control at a cross-head displacement rate of 0.5 mm/min. Two different types of test were carried out. In 'continuous' tests specimens were loaded to failure without interruption and photographs were taken at regular intervals. In 'discontinuous' tests, specimens were loaded incrementally to progressively higher stress levels and the reloading curves enabled the laminate stiffness as a function of damage to be recorded. It was found that the reloading curves were significantly non-linear, especially at higher stress levels and the stiffness measured was a best-fit tangent value close to the origin.

Figure 1 Schematic of (a) DCB and (b) ENF specimens showing relevant dimensions.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Fracture Mechanics Tests The G_{IC} and G_{IIC} values both increase with increasing urethane content. Figure 2 shows the G_{IC} value as a function of crack length and illustrates R-curve type behaviour which is a result of fibre bridging. Table 2 shows the mean G_{IC} values (averaged over the first 50 mm of crack growth) and G_{IIC} values, based on five specimens of each type. For all the data the standard deviation was between 5 and 10 % of the mean value.

Table 2 Fracture toughness as a function of urethane content

Percentage Urethane	G_{IC} , J/m ²	G_{IIC} , J/m ²
0	334	850
5	388	-
10	467	-
20	578	1167

Figure 2 Mode I interlaminar fracture toughness, G_{IC} as a function of crack length and urethane content showing increasing resistance as a result of fibre bridging.

4.2 Tests on Quasi-Isotropic Laminates

4.2.1 Damage onset and growth The sequence of damage events was characteristic of a quasi-isotropic laminate. The first damage was cracking in the 90° plies, occurring at a strain of about 0.25 % (applied stress of 60 MPa) in the unmodified epoxy laminate and at a strain of about 0.5 % (applied stress of 110 MPa) in the urethane-containing laminate, consistent with the experiments of Leaity et al [8] using simple crossply laminates from the same system. The crack density increased with further loading in both systems and is shown as a function of applied stress in Figure 3. Cracking in the 90° plies was followed by cracking in the surface 45° plies, then the (internal) -45° plies and subsequently by delamination. Figure 4 shows the delaminated area (measured from photographs of the front of the specimen) as a function of applied stress for the two systems. The delaminations occurred at the $-45/90$ interfaces and jogged from one side of the laminate midplane to the other, through the 90° ply cracks. Extrapolating the plots of delamination area against applied stress to the point where they intersect the stress axis gives the stresses for delamination onset in the two materials as 158 MPa in the epoxy system and 195 MPa in the epoxy/urethane system. These values are both likely to be slight overestimates (by about 5 %) because during the discontinuous tests, delamination cracking was noted at the edge of the specimens before it became visible at the front of the specimen, initially as separated small triangular shaped regions. At higher stresses these regions link to form a reasonably smooth

Figure 3 Transverse ply crack density as a function of applied stress in quasi-isotropic GFRP laminates containing unmodified epoxy and epoxy with 20 % urethane.

Figure 4 Delaminated area as a function of applied stress in quasi-isotropic GFRP laminates containing unmodified epoxy and epoxy with 20 % urethane.

delamination front which grows across the specimen under increasing applied stress. Associated with this advance there is an increase in matrix crack density behind the delamination crack front. Figure 5 enables a comparison to be made between the degree of damage in the two materials at a strain level of 1.6 % in continuous tests.

4.2.2 Stiffness reduction The initial modulus of the epoxy laminates is 26 GPa and for the urethane-containing laminates 24 GPa, compared with the laminated plate theory predictions of 26.3 GPa and 24.2 GPa respectively (based on the ply properties of Table 1). Figure 6 shows a plot of normalised stiffness as a function of applied stress for the quasi-isotropic laminates and this reflects the combined effects of intra-ply and inter-ply cracking. The modified epoxy system has a greater damage tolerance and so maintains a higher fraction of its initial (lower) stiffness than the unmodified epoxy system. Figure 7 shows normalised stiffness plotted against delamination area for the two systems. The initial drop before delamination starts is a result of matrix cracking in the 90° and 45° plies. The progressive reduction in stiffness with increasing delamination size is a result of the loss of coupling between the plies and further matrix cracking in the off-axis plies behind the delamination front. The effect of this combination and interaction of the damage modes on stiffness cannot be modelled in a simple way like the systems of O'Brien [1] and Poursartip [7] which show a more or less linear reduction in stiffness with delamination area.

Figure 5 Matrix cracking and delamination damage at 1.6 % applied strain in quasi-isotropic GFRP laminates containing (a) unmodified epoxy and (b) epoxy with 20 % urethane.

Figure 6 Normalised stiffness as a function of applied stress in quasi-isotropic GFRP laminates containing unmodified epoxy and epoxy with 20 % urethane.

Figure 7 Normalised stiffness as a function of normalised delamination area in quasi-isotropic GFRP laminates containing unmodified epoxy and epoxy with 20 % urethane.

4.2.3 Modelling of damage onset and growth The strain energy release rate, G , associated with crack growth can be found from the compliance equation

$$G = (P^2/2b)dc/da \quad (1)$$

where P is the load applied to a specimen containing a crack of length, a , and thickness, b , and dc/da is the rate of change of specimen compliance with crack length. Equation (1) can be written in terms of the change in normalised laminate stiffness (E/E_0) with normalised delamination area (A_D/WL , where A_D is the total delamination area in a length L of the coupon of width W) as

$$G = \left(\frac{\sigma^2}{E^2}\right) \frac{E_0 t}{2} \left[-\frac{d(E/E_0)}{d(A_D/WL)} \right] \quad (2)$$

where σ is the stress applied to the laminate and t is the laminate thickness. From the slope of the plots in Figure 7 and the data for the delamination area as a function of applied stress (Figure 4) the strain energy release rate associated with delamination growth can be found empirically using equation (2). Proceeding in this way we find that at delamination onset ($A_D \rightarrow 0$) the strain energy release rates are 1000 J/m^2 and 1450 J/m^2 for the unmodified system and the urethane-containing system respectively. These values are considerably higher than the G_{IC} and G_{IIC} values shown in Table 2, and would not be consistent with a linear G_I/G_{II} failure locus. The

reason for this is that matrix cracking in the 90° and 45° plies is occurring simultaneously with the delamination advance. Consequently the energy calculated using equation (2) represents that needed for the matrix cracking as well as the delamination. As the delamination proceeds further the total energy required (for the combined delamination and matrix cracking) can be represented using an R-curve type of analysis [1,7]. If we apply such an approach to the unmodified system we find that the resistance is approximately constant with a mean value of about 1050 J/m². For the urethane-containing system the resistance is constant up to a normalised delamination area of 20 %, with a mean value of about 1300 J/m². After this it appears to decrease. However the calculated resistance values are very sensitive to the measured slope of the normalised stiffness/normalised delamination area curve (in both systems) and further work is necessary to confirm these trends.

5. CONCLUDING REMARKS

The modification of the epoxy resin of a glass fibre reinforced composite increases both the Mode I and Mode II critical strain energy release rates. This in turn has the effect of lessening the amount of intra- and inter-laminar cracking in a (+45/-45/0/90)_s laminate at any given stress level under quasi-static loading. The effective crack resistance at any particular damage level, as calculated from the compliance equation expressed in terms of the delamination area, reflects both the energy required for delamination and that needed for matrix cracking. With the advantage of the transparent system used in the present work it should be possible to separate and model the individual components of the damage providing that stiffness relations appropriate to each damage type can be developed.

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